

TABLE 2—SELECTED IR BANDS (cm⁻¹)*

Compd **	O-H...O	CO+OH	NO	NO	Additional bands
HL'	2 800-1 750v	1 525s, 1 270s, 880s	1 320s	820s	-
NaSalA HL'	2 3°0 2 34, 1 900br	1 492s, 1 260s, 868s	1 308s	815s	708s
LiAnc HL'	1 900br	1 498sh, 1 250sh, 860s, 1 490s	1 310m	815s	700s
NaAnc HL'	2 350-2 28, 1 900br	1 500s, 1 260s 865s	1 305m	815s	690s
KAnc.HL'	2 350br	1 520m, 1 255s, 865s	1 315s	812s	718m
Li1N2N.HL'	2 350br	1 525m, 1 280s, 875w	1 215m	820s	728sh
K1N2N.HL'	2 350br	1 525s, 1 270s, 870m	1 305w	820s	728vw

*v - variable bands, vw - very weak, s - strong, sh - shoulder

**Explanation as in Table 1.

N-O bending mode too shifted to lower frequencies by 5-10 cm⁻¹. These features suggest coordination of the ligand through the oxygen atom of the N-O moiety. A new broad band of weak to medium intensity in the region 2 400-1 900 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes, which could be attributed to O-H...O absorption, suggests the hydrogen bonding to be an essential feature of these complexes.

Molar conductivities were measured in DMF at 23° at a concentration of 10⁻³M. A value of ca 35-40 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ is indicative of a 1:1 electrolyte⁹. None of the complexes approach molar conductance value for 1:1 electrolyte. The slightly higher values for the potassium complexes imply that they have undergone partial dissociation in the solvent used.

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Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) Benzilates with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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THE present paper reports the complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} benzilate with *N*-base quinoline and β-picoline in continuation of our previous works¹⁻³

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Aqueous solution of metal (Cu, Ni, Zn, Co) salts were mixed separately with alcoholic solution of benzoic acid when metal benzilates were precipitated, which were filtered under suction, washed with small quantity of alcohol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Metal benzilates were refluxed with quinoline and β-picoline separately in ethanol medium for 0.5 h. The volume of the solution was reduced to 5 ml by a rotary vacuum evaporator and kept overnight. The crystalline compounds that separated out were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried in vacuum desiccator. Metal and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Analytical data of the complexes were presented in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF METAL BENZILATE COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.	$\Omega^{-1} \Lambda_M$ cm ²
			Metal	N		
CoL ₂ Q ₂	Blue	158	7.45 (7.65)	3.25 (3.63)	4.6	8.6
CoL ₂ (β -pic) ₄	Pink	162	7.12 (6.66)	5.89 (6.33)	5.1	6.2
NiL ₂ Q ₂	Green	165	7.38 (7.62)	3.36 (3.63)	3.1	5.8
NiL ₂ (β -pic) ₄	Green	168	6.21 (6.64)	5.95 (6.33)	3.2	8.8
Cu L ₂ Q ₂	Blue	146	8.41 (8.22)	3.46 (3.61)	1.79	10.2
Cu L ₂ (β -pic) ₂	Blue	149	9.25 (9.03)	3.62 (3.98)	1.8	9.6
Zn L ₂ Q ₂	White	154	8.62 (8.41)	3.71 (3.60)	—	10.5
Zn L ₂ (β -pic) ₂	White	156	8.85 (9.23)	3.71 (3.98)	—	9.8

* L = Benzilate, Q = Quinoline, B = (pic) = 3 methyl pyridine.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are crystalline having fairly low melting point and are soluble in common organic solvents. Acetone solution of the compounds have low molar conductance values indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

In the infrared spectra, benzoic acid⁴ has the $\nu_{C=O}$ band at 1650 cm⁻¹, which shifts to lower frequency region in metal benzilates at 1625–1630 cm⁻¹. In the base adducts, this band shifts slightly to the higher frequency region at 1635–1640 cm⁻¹ due to coordination of the σ -bonding nitrogen bases to the metal ion. In addition, most of the bands due to the free nitrogen ligand either shift or are modified, indicating bonding to the metal ion. This has been corroborated by the observation⁵ of ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} at 465 and 385 cm⁻¹, respectively.

In the visible electronic spectra, Co^{II}-benzilate complex with quinoline exhibits one intense band at 16.0 kK assignable⁶ to $4A_2 \rightarrow 4T_1(P)$ transition. On the basis of the position and intensity of the absorption band and magnetic moment data, this complex has presumably a tetrahedral configuration which is supported by $\mu_{eff} = 4.6$ B.M. The other cobalt complex has bands around 19.5 and 20.0 kK regions attributable⁷ to $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ transition, suggesting a possible octahedral geometry of the complex. In case of Ni^{II} complexes, bands are observed in the regions 9.6–9.8, 13.5–13.8 and 24.8–25.2 kK due to $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(F)$, $\rightarrow 3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively suggesting⁸ an octahedral environment around the metal ion in conformity with the magnetic moment values 3.1–3.2 B.M. Cu^{II} complexes have a broad absorption band in the regions 18.4–18.6 kK, indicating⁹ a four coordinated square-planar configuration. μ_{eff} for Cu^{II} complex was in the normal range 1.79–1.80 B.M. Zn^{II} complexes are presumed to be tetrahedral on the

basis of their analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data.

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A Study on the Thermal Decomposition of some Metal Dithiocarbamate Complexes†

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THERMAL decomposition of nickel(II), zinc(II), cadmium(II), chromium(III) and cobalt(III) complexes with *N*-methylbenzylidithiocarbamate and morpholine-4-carbodithioate has been studied by

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